

FROM THE LENS OF THE COMMUNITY STAKEHOLDERS: THE PEACE AND ORDER PROGRAM OF THE PHILIPPINE NATIONAL POLICE (PNP)

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the experiences of the community stakeholders on the peace and order program of the Philippine National Police (PNP) specifically to assess the impact of the peace and order program of the PNP on the community; and the aspirations of the informants to improve the peace and order program implemented by the PNP. This study employs a qualitative phenomenological approach, utilizing ten (10) informants from community stakeholders in Barangay Cogon and Poblacion III, Tagbilaran City, Bohol, using a validated interview guide with open-ended questions prepared by the researcher. The informants were all interviewed individually. Colaizzi's analysis was used to analyze the data collected. The themes formulated for the positive experiences were: Active Police Presence, Collaborative Policing, and Integrated Crime Prevention. For the negative experiences: Operational Gaps, Persistent Social Threats, and Declining Public Trust. To assess the impact on the peace and order program of the Philippine National Police (PNP) on community stakeholders, the researcher created three (3) themes: Optimized Police Visibility, Community-Integrated Police Force, and Strong Business Confidence. Lastly, for the aspirations of the informants to improve the peace and order program implemented by the PNP: Deepening Civic Bonds, Pursuit for Good Police Image, and Leveraging Technology for Better Policing. This will serve as supplementary guidelines for evidence-based policies, strategies, and training programs tailored to the unique needs and contexts of the Philippine National Police.

Keywords: *Philippine National Police, Peace and Order Program, Views of Community Stakeholders, Criminal Justice, Tagbilaran City, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The foundation of humanity's survival is peace. It is vital to ensure the peace and security of the people and to maintain economic development, social order, and political stability. An environment of peace and order encourages investment, creates more job possibilities, and draws more tourists. In general, economic development refers to the consistent, coordinated efforts of communities and policymakers to raise the standard of living and financial well-being of a particular region. The absence of hostility is referred to as peace. It refers to an environment characterized by healthy interpersonal and international relationships, as well as acknowledgment of equality and fairness. Peace must include justice in a society.

The vision of the Philippine National Police (PNP) by 2030 is to have a safer place to live, work, and do business to help build a country that is a safe and conducive place to carry out business and other economic activities. This vision reflects the PNP's goal to be a highly capable, effective, and credible police service, working in partnership with a responsive community by 2030 with the aid of the Almighty (Philippine National Police [PNP], n.d.).

The peace and order situation in the Philippines is an essential duty and responsibility of the Philippine National Police (PNP), as the Philippine Constitution mandates that the state shall establish national police, which is civilian in character and national in scope. The Philippine government has recognized the vital role of internal security and the maintenance of peace and order in nation-building.

The government must ensure that all Filipinos feel secure to walk and travel around all places in the country, without fear of harm to themselves and their property, and can go about their business, economic, and social pursuits. Moreover, as the country pursues greater economic development, the government must safeguard national interests, territory, and sovereignty.

This vision aligns with the mission of the Philippine National Police (PNP), which has been shaped by the enactment of Republic Act (RA) No 6975, as amended by RA No. 8551, and as further amended by RA No. 9708 which gave a clear mandate to the PNP in enforcing the law, preventing and controlling crimes, maintaining peace and order, and ensuring public safety & internal security with the active support of the community.

Fighting against criminality and insurgency to obtain a peaceful and orderly Bohol has the Provincial Peace and Order Council (PPOC) setting aside a war-chest of P419,008,047 for Bohol's 2023 peace and order programs. Convened at the Ceremonial Hall of the new Provincial Capitol, the PPOC, which was presided by Governor Erico Aristotle Aumentado and attended by Vice Governor Victor Dionisio Balite, along with its

45 member agencies and sectoral representatives, identified the 55 peace and order projects and programs that would bring the government to the communities (Bohol Island News, 2023).

As a criminologist and a member of the academe, the researcher feels the need to address issues about peace and order in our community. Thus, this study generally seeks to explore the perspectives of community stakeholders on the peace and order program of the PNP, particularly the experiences of the informants on the PNP's peace and order program, the impact of the peace and order program to the community, and aspirations of the informants of the peace and order program implemented by the PNP. The study is socially relevant as it addresses public concerns about crime and safety, offering a platform for community members to voice their experiences and participate in shaping the policies that affect their daily lives. Thus, this research not only supports better police strategies but also encourages a more inclusive and collaborative approach to maintaining peace and order.

Research Questions

This study explored the experiences of the community stakeholders of the peace and order program of the Philippine National Police (PNP) in Tagbilaran City, Bohol.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the informants on the peace and order program of the PNP?
2. What is the impact of the peace and order program of the PNP to the community?
3. What are the aspirations of the informants to improve the peace and order program implemented by the PNP?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Bohol, Philippines. The researcher carefully and circumspectly chose ten (10) informants who could disclose experiences as beneficiaries of the peace and order program of the PNP. The researcher has identified ten (10) individuals from the designated study locale who have at least 2 years of residency in their respective barangay. These participants are community stakeholders of the peace and order program of the PNP, which includes four (4) residents, two (2) professionals, two (2) business owners, and two (2) members of the Barangay Peacekeeping Action Teams (BPAT). All of the ten (10) informants were subjected to an in-depth interview, and no focused group discussion was utilized during the collection of data.

The researcher crafted and used a semi-structured interview guide in conducting in-depth interviews aimed at exploring the perception of the beneficiaries of the peace and order program of the PNP. The first part of the questionnaire explored the experiences of the informants on the PNP's peace and order program. The second part examines the impact of the PNP's peace and order program on the community. In

contrast, the third part delves into the aspirations of the informants regarding the program implemented by the PNP.

The data collection methods used in this research include in-depth interviews to gather relevant information. The researcher extracted exact data to respond to the sub-problems. The researcher utilized an audio recorder and field notes to ensure accurate records during the in-depth interview. Transcription of verbatim recordings preceded data analysis, addressing sub-problems effectively. The data gathered from the informants during the in-depth interview was analyzed through Colaizzi's 7 steps of data analysis. The responses of the participants during the interview were transcribed and translated individually. From the interview transcriptions, significant statements were extracted and core meanings were formulated. The formulated meanings with commonalities or common key ideas were then grouped into clustered themes.

RESULTS

The following twelve (12) emergent themes were developed to provide a clearer understanding on the experiences of the community stakeholders of the peace and order program of the Philippine National Police (PNP).

Research Questions	Emergent Themes
I. Experiences of the Informants on the Peace and Order Program of the PNP	
A. Positive Experiences	1. Active Police Presence
	2. Collaborative Policing
	3. Integrated Crime Prevention
B. Negative Experiences	1. Operational Gaps
	2. Persistent Social Threats
	3. Declining Public Trust
II. Impact of the Peace and Order Program of the PNP to the Community	
	1. Optimized Police Visibility
	2. Community-Integrated Police Force
	3. Strong Business Confidence
III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve the Peace and Order Program Implemented by the PNP	

	1. Deepening Civic Bonds
	2. Pursuit for Good Police Image
	3. Leveraging Technology for Better Policing

DISCUSSION

I. Experiences of the Informants on the Peace and Order Program of the PNP

A. Positive Experiences:

1. Active Police Presence: This theme represents the observation of the informants on how the visible and consistent police presence in their community gives them a greater sense of safety and security. Many of the informants expressed their sense of security during the day and night because of the visibility of the police officers in their community. The informants also mentioned that active presence leads to quicker response times and helps prevent conflicts before they escalate, reassuring that security measures are in order.

Informant 1 mentioned that:

So, for the PNP, based on my experience ma'am, I feel that it's really secured. I feel secured because their police visibility is very strong, especially at night and also during the day. They are conducting checkpoints, and I think as a resident of Tagbilaran, they are not just sticking to the highways. They are also positioned at the entry points of the city (IDI1:SS1).

This theme is anchored on the Situational Crime Prevention theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), which is a crime reduction strategy that focuses on reducing the opportunities for crime by altering the immediate environment. A visible and engaged police force can directly influence the situational factors that make crime more difficult or risky to commit. This serves as a deterrent to potential offenders by increasing the perceived risk of being caught. When police officers are regularly seen patrolling neighborhoods, monitoring hotspots, or interacting with the community, it disrupts criminal planning and reduces the likelihood of offenses occurring.

As a result, the informants feel that their community is safe because of active police presence. Furthermore, it fosters trust, encourages cooperation, and strengthens relationships between police officers and the community.

In the study of Chokprachakchat (2011), police officers are one of several occupations vital to the country's economic and social development because they have a crucial role in keeping the peace, maintaining public security, and preserving common

property for community members, all of which are essential physical needs in human society.

2. Collaborative Policing: This theme emphasizes strong partnerships and shared responsibilities between police agencies and community stakeholders to address public safety issues effectively. It goes beyond traditional police outreach or information sharing by involving joint decision-making, resource sharing, and coordinated problem-solving efforts.

Informant 3 recalled:

In Tagbilaran City, my positive experience with the Philippine National Police (PNP) is their collaboration with the barangay tanods, especially during night patrols. They include us even during checkpoints, so there's transparency which is important, so it's not only them, but also within the barangay. Also, it's easy to communicate with them, sometimes we're even friends. And the security measures, especially at night, within the vicinity of Poblacion III, are well observed (IDI3:SS7).

This theme is also supported by the General Systems Theory of Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1968) which promotes partnerships and shared responsibility for public safety. Police officers, community members, and other stakeholders communicate, coordinate, and pool their resources to address crime and disorder. This integrated approach recognizes that public safety challenges are complex and require input and cooperation from multiple sectors.

The informants suggested to include their local unit in patrolling, as they are more familiar with their community areas. Additionally, there are tailored-fit programs for both youth and adults, which aid in implementing the peace and order program. These joint efforts embody the Situation Crime Prevention principle of increasing guardianship and reducing opportunities for crime. This builds trust, improves communication, and creates more effective, sustainable solutions to crime and public safety challenges by leveraging the strengths and resources of the whole community.

3. Integrated Crime Prevention: Instead of relying solely on traditional policing methods, this strategy brings together law enforcement, local government units, schools, social services, businesses, and community organizations to develop comprehensive solutions. The informants mentioned that the peace and order program is well maintained in their community, which means that their public security and safety measures are in place to monitor individuals.

Informant 8 stated that:

I'm okay with their programs, especially since they focus on maintaining public safety and security. This also helps ensure that students stay out of trouble, particularly within the school environment (IDI8:SS25).

This theme is anchored on the Situational Crime Prevention theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), which combines multiple strategies, agencies, and community efforts to prevent crime in a coordinated and holistic manner. It recognizes that no single method or organization can address all aspects of crime, so it brings together law enforcement, local government, social services, community groups, and environmental design to create a comprehensive crime prevention plan. This provides the practical, environment-focused tools that can be embedded within integrated crime prevention programs, ensuring that efforts to reduce crime are both targeted and comprehensive. This makes crime prevention more effective and sustainable, as it addresses both the symptoms and root causes of criminal behavior.

B. Negative Experiences:

1. Operational Gaps: This theme focuses on the weaknesses of the implementation of the peace and order program, deficiencies or shortcomings in the implementation, coordination, and effectiveness of crime prevention and law enforcement activities that hinder achieving optimal public safety outcomes. As mentioned by the informants, there are poor communications, inadequate manpower, and delays in responses to some situations. Some informants from the local unit expressed fear about the risks of handling conflict situations that may escalate without police presence, and they believe their limited resources hinder their ability to respond effectively to incidents.

Informant 3 recalled:

My first-hand experience as a Barangay Chief Tanod is that whenever there's a call for help, we're the first ones to respond. But honestly, it's not easy for us, because all we carry are batons or sticks, while the suspects are usually armed with knives. It's risky and scary for us, since we're always the first ones sent into the situation. I just hope there would be times when the police could be the ones to go in first, but their reasoning is that we know the area better, so we should lead the way. Still, it's a tough and dangerous task for us (IDI3:SS42).

This theme is anchored by the Situational Crime Prevention theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), which pertained to the idea that crime can be reduced by making changes to the immediate environment, thereby limiting opportunities for offending. However, the weaknesses or shortcomings in the implementation of crime prevention measures can undermine the effectiveness of the strategies as they breed weak coordination, insufficient training, and resources.

This is supported by the General Systems Theory of Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1968), which views organizations, communities, or programs as complex systems made up of interconnected and interdependent parts. For a system to function effectively, all its components must work together harmoniously. An operational gap occurs when there is a breakdown, weakness, or missing link in the processes, communication, or resources within the system. In a peace and order program, if the police, local government, and community organizations do not share information or coordinate their actions, crime prevention efforts may fail, even if each group is working hard on its own.

2. Persistent Social Threats: This contributes to a cycle of crime and unrest, making communities more vulnerable and undermining the effectiveness of peace and order programs. Many of the informants are concerned with the rampant drug-related activities in their community. One shared that a resident reported to their local unit regarding issues with repacking drugs inside their room. Another informant was also frustrated to see known drug users who are freely roaming around in their area.

Informant 10 complained:

The worsening drug problem. I actually know some of the addicts in our area. Before, they were kept off the streets, but now they're just walking around freely again it's like they were never dealt with (IDI10:SS76).

According to Situational Crime Prevention theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), actionable tools to mitigate persistent social threats by altering the physical and social environment reduce the opportunities for crime and help communities regain a sense of safety and order. This theory suggests that crime is not only the result of individual motivation but also of situational factors that make committing a crime easier, more rewarding, or less risky.

This is supported by the General Systems Theory of Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1968), which views society as a complex system made up of interconnected parts, including individuals, families, institutions, and government agencies that must work together to maintain balance and functionality. These issues do not exist in isolation, they are symptoms of deeper systemic problems, such as weak governance, lack of education, poor health services, and insufficient economic opportunities.

3. Declining Public Trust: This theme was created to represent the answers of the informants regarding their concerns, such as delays in responses and leniency towards drug-related cases. This refers to the loss of confidence that people have in institutions, particularly in law enforcement and government bodies tasked with maintaining peace and order.

Informant 10 expressed:

I won't compare them to other government agencies, but I honestly don't understand why authorities seem so relaxed when it comes to drug-related issues. Drugs are the number one concern for people right now, and it seems like some police officers are turning a blind eye. This is a huge problem because their main duty is to protect society (IDI10:SS82).

This is anchored by the Situational Crime Prevention Theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), a key element of this theory is the role of guardianship, which often relies on the cooperation and vigilance of the public. When public trust in law enforcement or community safety institutions declines, people are less likely to report suspicious activities, cooperate with police, or participate in community watch programs. This

undermines the guardianship and collective efficacy that are crucial for situational crime prevention.

A study by Hinds (2009) investigates the impact of people's overall views and experiences with police, both citizen-initiated and police-initiated, on public satisfaction with Australian cops. The findings are supported by data from US-based studies showing a link between police contact dissatisfaction and decreased public trust in law enforcement.

II. Impact of the Peace and Order Program of the PNP to the Community

Based on the responses of the informants, three (3) themes were developed.

1. Optimized Police Visibility: The informants mentioned that the implementation of the said program was exemplary because the police are obvious in conducting patrols around the area. A comparison was also made on the changes of crime rates from the previous years to the present as a result of the efficient implementation of the peace and order program.

Informant 7 stated that:

When it comes to the police, they respond directly to calls, which I believe discourages potential wrongdoers since they know the police are involved. That's really the main thing I've observed as of now, there seems to be less, almost no, crime in our area. That's just my observation though; I can't speak for the entire barangay since it's quite large. But from what I've personally seen, it feels peaceful (IDI7:SS102).

Anchored by the Situational Crime Prevention theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), this theme emphasizes altering the immediate environment to make crime less attractive, notably by increasing the perceived risk of detection and apprehension for potential offenders. High police visibility, such as frequent patrols, marked vehicles, and visible enforcement activities, serves as a deterrent by signaling to offenders that the risk of being caught is elevated.

Sumad-on (2021) emphasizes the responsibility of police officers in upholding peace and order, ensuring that communities are shielded from lawlessness and disorder.

2. Community-Integrated Police Force: This theme reflects the social cohesion among community members, which helps maintain the peace and order program. Many expressed that whenever there are incidents in their neighborhood, the locals would contact the police officers immediately. Informants highlighted that such integration encourages open communication, mutual respect, and collaborative problem-solving, which are essential for addressing both crime and underlying social issues.

Informant 2 shared:

Each purok has its own dedicated team. I'm very happy that the community cooperates, because without the people's involvement, there's very little we can accomplish. The residents are really the key players here. Because of everyone's participation, crime has been minimized, almost eliminated (IDI2:SS117).

This is anchored by Situational Crime Prevention theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), which focuses on modifying the immediate environment to make criminal activities less appealing, more difficult, or riskier to commit. This includes strategies such as improving lighting, increasing surveillance, controlling access to certain areas, and promoting community guardianship. This builds trust and social bonds, which are essential for sustaining situational interventions. Residents are more likely to report suspicious activities, maintain communal spaces, and support police initiatives.

According to Jeffery (1972), the importance of community involvement in crime prevention aligns with the principles of Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED), which advocates for collaboration between the police and the community to enhance safety.

3. Strong Business Confidence: Many of the informants mentioned that the businesses in the city are booming and thriving. This confidence encourages economic growth, investment, and expansion, as entrepreneurs are more willing to commit resources in areas where law enforcement is responsive and security measures are reliable. In turn, a safe business environment generates employment, stimulates local economies, and contributes to overall community development.

Informant 1 stated that:

Well, for us, with the implementation of the PNP peace and order programs, we've experienced something. I think we already have 24-hour stores, right? That's really something. Why are they open 24 hours? Maybe because they feel safe with our PNP peace and order program. And it's not just the 24/7 stores, we also have pharmacies, and we also have small shops, what do you call them, sari-sari stores that now close much later because maybe they feel safe. That's why they close late, so our economy has also boomed. I think that's one thing we can list as an economic benefit. Another thing is, I think there are only a few stores here that are equipped with guards. So, fewer guards mean you're confident that your establishment is safe (IDI1:SS165).

This is anchored by Situational Crime Prevention theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), which suggests that one way of reducing opportunities for crime is by making environmental and managerial changes that increase the effort and risk for offenders, reduce rewards, and remove excuses for criminal behavior. This encourages businesses to tailor security measures to specific risks and crime types relevant to their operations, which ensures that resources are used efficiently and that protection is maximized. This structured, proactive approach to crime prevention helps businesses feel more in control

of their security environment, leading to greater confidence in their ability to prevent and respond to crime.

This theme is supported by General Systems Theory of Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1968), which encourages looking beyond isolated security measures to consider the entire business environment as an integrated system. Security confidence arises not just from individual controls but from how these controls interact with people, processes, technology, and external factors to maintain secure operations. This holistic perspective helps identify vulnerabilities that might be overlooked when focusing on components in isolation.

III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve the Peace and Order Program Implemented by the PNP

1. Deepening Civic Bonds: This emerged as a vital theme from the insights of community stakeholders, highlighting the growing importance of strong relationships between citizens and institutions in maintaining peace and order. Informants consistently emphasized that mutual trust, cooperation, and active participation are essential in addressing local issues and ensuring community safety. Strengthening the relationship between the government, particularly law enforcement agencies, and the community. This approach encourages active citizen participation in maintaining peace, safety, and security at the local level.

Informant 2 said that:

During barangay activities like symposiums or assemblies, it's important to ensure there's always a representative from the PNP present. Someone who can directly provide information, explain their services, share advice, and discuss policies. Their presence really helps build trust and strengthens their reach to the community (IDI2:SS200).

This theme is also supported by General Systems Theory of Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1968) which provides a framework to understand how these bonds interact with broader social structures and processes, emphasizing the importance of dynamic relationships, feedback, and balance for sustaining healthy, inclusive communities. This explanation draws primarily on the conceptual framework and findings outlined in the generative theory of social cohesion and civic integration, which applies systems thinking to social bonds and community dynamics.

According to Jeffery (1972), the importance of community involvement in crime prevention aligns with the principles of Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED), which advocates for collaboration between the police and the community to enhance safety.

2. Pursuit for Good Police Image: This theme was created to represent the responses of the informants' growing demand from the community for professional, accountable, and transparent institutions that not only enforce the law but also embody integrity, efficiency, and responsiveness. From the perspective of the community

stakeholders, institutional excellence means equipping police forces with proper training, modern tools, and ethical standards while also ensuring internal accountability and community-centered practices.

Informant 9 stated that:

And to answer your question, what should the police do is I said it earlier that it takes a little bit of restructuring, changing the mindset of its personnel so that in order for them to embody their motto to serve and protect, to serve and protect the interest of the public (IDI9:SS211).

This theme is supported by Low Profile theory of Lawrence W. Sherman (1980), which suggests maintaining a discreet, modest presence to avoid attracting undue attention or resistance, which can be particularly relevant in sensitive peace and order contexts where overt actions might provoke conflict. Pursuing excellence requires practical, often visible actions such as community engagement, transparent reporting, and strong leadership. However, applying low-profile theory means these actions are carried out with discretion to avoid escalating tensions or alienating stakeholders, especially in conflict-prone areas. This balance helps sustain peace efforts without provoking opposition by balancing visible, high-quality performance with discreet, sensitive implementation. This fosters trust, minimizes conflict, and supports sustainable peace and security outcomes.

Charbonneau and Riccucci (2008) propose indicators of social equity. It means that measures of the effectiveness and efficiency of police performance in community policing should include standards of fair treatment of people, also known as procedural justice.

It is a universally accepted norm that the police service can only achieve professionalism if it genuinely respects the rights of every citizen, regardless of race, culture, belief, or social status. Promoting and protecting human rights is critical to the country's peace and order, public safety, and the rule of law (Stürmer et al., 2013).

3. Leveraging Technology for Better Policing: The informants pointed out that technological tools such as CCTV surveillance, real-time communication systems, and digital reporting platforms are used. Digital tools also make it possible for law enforcers and the community to coordinate more effectively, which results in faster interventions and better-informed decision-making. In general, informants viewed the use of technology in policing as a deliberate move toward safer, more intelligent, and more community-responsive law enforcement, rather than merely a modernization endeavor.

Informant 10 shared:

While it's true that homeowners aren't required by law to install security cameras, having even one or two installed can make a big difference. There are many affordable options now that allow you to monitor your home remotely through your phone, as long as you have internet access. This is especially helpful considering that our police are

often outnumbered by the population. Ideally, every family would produce a police officer, but that's not the reality, so helping through early reporting and using surveillance tools like CCTVs is a great support (IDI10:SS197).

This is based on the Situational Crime Prevention theory of Ronald Clarke (1980), which focuses on reducing opportunities for crime through changes to the immediate environment. It aims to increase the risks for offenders and decrease the rewards of criminal activity. Technology plays a crucial role in improving these strategies by enabling faster coordination and responses to incidents. This minimizes the time offenders have to commit crimes, makes environments less conducive to crime, increases the chances of detection, and empowers both law enforcement and the community to prevent and respond to criminal activity more effectively.

Conclusions

The study concludes that the Peace and Order Program of the PNP plays a crucial role in promoting community safety through active police presence, collaborative efforts, and integrated crime prevention. These strategies contribute to improved police visibility, stronger community integration, and increased business confidence. However, challenges such as operational gaps, persistent social threats, and declining public trust remain and must be addressed.

The aspirations of the informants highlight the need to deepen civic bonds, enhance the police image, and utilize technology to improve policing services. Overall, strengthening partnerships between the PNP and the community, alongside continuous program improvements, is essential in sustaining peace, building trust, and ensuring long-term public safety and development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

This study can be helpful to the Philippine National Police (PNP) to have an understanding of how the experiences of the community stakeholders perceive the implementation of the peace and order program, updating its operations with an emphasis on community involvement, professionalization, and rights-based policing. Initiatives for maintaining peace and order, like visiting the barangay in their extension programs, will be more effective and popular if relationships with local communities and other stakeholders are strengthened.

The Local Government Unit (LGU), in collaboration with the Philippine National Police (PNP) and the community, will implement a more cohesive public safety strategy. This involves both entities working hand in hand with the community through their extension programs to maintain peace and order. Importantly, the Local Government Unit (LGU) should also allocate a budget for these programs. They are also challenged to

encourage the trust and involvement of the community in the consistent implementation of peace and order.

The Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) can have bases to enhance and ensure a more inclusive, community-driven policy. Strengthen monitoring, evaluation, and support systems to ensure consistent and effective implementation of peace and order programs nationwide.

Barangay officials need to enhance their competence in executing peace and order ordinances and foster greater cooperation with constituents to overcome challenges such as a lack of awareness. Officials should actively involve the community in peace and order initiatives, practicing a proactive way of safety and security, leveraging local knowledge and resources for more effective and sustainable outcomes.

The community stakeholders are encouraged to participate in peace and order programs, support local ordinances, and collaborate with authorities to build trust and ensure safety. Raising awareness of peace and order regulations and empowering individuals to report issues and participate in solutions are crucial for community resilience and crime prevention.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical considerations surrounding the research about the Peace and Order Program of the PNP impose inherent ethical responsibilities to minimize harm and enhance benefits. In this study, which explored the experiences of the informants on the PNP's peace and order program, the commitment to ethical conduct is of utmost importance. The beneficence of the study was established through open communication which strengthens police-community relations, reduces conflicts, and ensures programs were ethical and effective. The non-maleficence includes protecting the community stakeholders from possible risks such as psychological distress or breaches of confidentiality. A strong ethical protocol was put in place by the researcher to protect participants' emotional and mental well-being and guarantee that their rights and privacy are protected at all times during the research process. Justice was represented through the diverse perspectives and experiences within the community accurately, avoided any biases or prejudices that could compromise the integrity of the research findings. While autonomy was established by obtaining voluntary and informed consent from all the participants, clearly explaining the purpose, risks, and benefits of the study, and providing assurances of confidentiality and anonymity.

The bracketing and reflexivity were also established in the conduct of the research. As an instructor in the College of Criminal Justice, this research, the experiences of the community stakeholders of the peace and order program of the Philippine National Police (PNP) in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, required a careful acknowledgment of potential personal predispositions. This increases intricacy and necessitates continuous reflection and self-awareness during the study process. Recognizing and mitigating the potential influence

of personal biases on data collection, analysis, and interpretation is crucial to uphold the research's credibility and thoroughness.

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